

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SYSTEM FOR REGULATING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF UNEMPLOYED YOUTH IN SYRDARYA REGION

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ABSTRACT

This thesis analyzes the measures being taken to increase the competitiveness of unemployed youth in the labor market of Syrdarya region, regulatory mechanisms, and their level of effectiveness. Also, taking into account the vocational training of youth, employment programs, and regional characteristics, the strengths and weaknesses of the system are identified and proposals are put forward to increase efficiency..

Introduction

Today, the problem of unemployment in the labor market, especially among young people, is one of the most pressing issues. The “Youth Policy” programs, “Every Family is an Entrepreneur” and the “Youth Notebook” and “Youth our Future” initiatives adopted at the level of the Republic of Uzbekistan are important mechanisms for ensuring the employment of unemployed youth. Syrdarya region, in terms of its economic potential, has developed as an agro-industrial region in the republic and has its own characteristics in ensuring youth employment. Therefore, assessing the effectiveness of the system for regulating the competitiveness of unemployed youth in the regional labor market is of urgent scientific and practical importance.

In almost all countries with a developed market economy, the state seeks to transform the employment service into a highly effective structure that ensures both the competitiveness of unemployed youth and, on this basis, their employment, and the implementation of the functions of this service, including the justification of the large amounts of funds allocated to the above-mentioned direction of active employment policy. In our opinion, this approach serves to ensure openness and transparency of labor market processes. It relies not only on statistical indicators, but also makes it possible to assess real added value through economic criteria. Therefore, this is one of the most acceptable approaches.

Discussion

The range of criteria used to determine the effectiveness of employment services also includes the number of people who have used these services. For example:

- assist citizens in finding work that matches their qualifications and desires;
- provide temporary employment through the organization of public works;
- determine the level of imbalance in the labor market (i.e., the number of unemployed people for each vacant job);
- implement measures to temporarily engage minors aged 14–18;

- provide temporary employment to citizens aged 16–20 who have recently graduated from vocational colleges or secondary specialized educational institutions and are looking for work for the first time;
- temporary employment of citizens who have difficulty finding work;
- provision of professional counseling and guidance services to citizens;
- psychological support to the unemployed;
- organization of job fairs;
- holding special events for the adaptation of unemployed persons to society;
- provision of necessary assistance to citizens who wish to become self-employed.

A sociological study was conducted to determine the professions and jobs preferred by graduates of vocational schools and Gulistan State University in Syrdarya region. The research data indicate the importance of services that increase the competitiveness of young people entering the labor market in the eyes of employers. In particular, more than 70 percent of graduates of secondary specialized and vocational schools and about 20 percent of graduates of higher education institutions assessed their level of theoretical knowledge as low or average. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Assessment of the level of theoretical preparation, %

The analysis of Figure 1 shows that graduates of higher education institutions assessed their level of theoretical preparation as high, while among graduates of vocational colleges, opinions on this issue were mostly average.

The sociological study also assessed the level of practical preparation of graduates (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Assessment of the level of practical training, %

According to the analysis of Figure 2, among graduates of higher educational institutions, the number of those who assessed their practical training as “very high” is significantly higher than among graduates of vocational colleges. The number of those who considered their practical training to be “high” and “average” prevailed in vocational colleges.

These trends require strengthening the innovative partnership “higher educational institution - science - production” in educational institutions of the region, especially at Gulistan State University.

Studying the effectiveness and developing proposals:

The main goal of measures to increase the competitiveness of unemployed youth in the labor market is to provide them with jobs and attract new labor to various sectors of the economy.

However, since this process requires a large amount of material, labor and financial resources, important questions arise regarding the effectiveness of employment services and the social benefit of the allocated funds.

On the one hand, in our opinion, the very word employment indicates efficiency from a social point of view, that is, in this case, the unemployed person early enters social production, begins to contribute to the creation of material goods and services, and thereby generates income. In addition, a person feels a sense of satisfaction that through his labor activity he benefits not only those around him, but also himself, which increases his self-confidence and leads to a higher assessment of his position in society. As a result, such positive psychological changes contribute to a decrease in negative situations such as crime, drug addiction and alcoholism. After all, young people who pursue their professional goals and are busy with activities are usually far from such vices. In this regard, we propose to introduce the following

indicators of assessing the social efficiency of increasing the competitiveness of unemployed youth:

$$I_{jd} = J_{yos} / R_{yosh} \quad (1)$$

J_{yos} – Number of young people who have found jobs (persons) among those who participated in activities aimed at increasing competitiveness.

R_{yosh} – Number of unemployed youth participating in activities to increase competitiveness (persons).

$$T_d = R_{yosh} / R_{yos} \quad (2)$$

T_d – level of demand for programs and services that serve to increase competitiveness (%);

R_{yos} – Number of officially registered unemployed youth (persons).

Conclusion

The availability of the above indicators is useful in two ways: on the one hand, it allows for a clear assessment of the effectiveness of employment promotion organizations in this area; on the other hand, it encourages unemployed youth to participate in such programs, increasing their motivation when necessary.

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